

What can contemporary USA learn from the history of Portuguese imperial power in Japan
and in Brazil?

by

By Joaquim de Castro & Floyd Rudmin

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Introduction

The current paper displays the Portuguese intercultural relationships with two different cultures, e.g., Brazil and Japan. The relationship with Brazil will be described by two key scholars; Gilberto Freyre (1986/1933) and Roger Bastide (1971, 1973). The relationship with Japan will be reported by the Jesuit Luis de Fróis (1976, 1981, 1982, 1983, 1984/1594, 1993a/b/1585, 2001/1564) and by the novelist Fernão Mendes Pinto (1989/1614).

According to Dupront (1997), crusades were the precursors of the European colonialism. Portugal started the Western globalization (Gunn, 2003). Crusades, as the Portuguese occupation of Ceuta in 1415, implied a violent approach and a social dominance point of view (Sidanius, & Pratto, 1999). Furthermore, crusades also encompassed ethnocentric and Eurocentric approaches (Goody, 2006; Hall, 1992; Maalouf, 1999).

History and individual memory are always under revision (Loewenberg, 1996), and to rewrite history is part of History and of historiography (Braudel, 1958). The historical narrative does not provide experimental and measured evidence. However, it provides collective and cultural experiences that are shaping individual behavior and perception of “reality”. The literature of Social Representations of History (László, 2008; Liu, & Hilton, 2005; Liu, & László, 2007) reports how cultural borders shape behavior (Barth, 1969) and perception of ‘reality’.

The current article compares two colonial empires. It states that the Anglo-Saxon Empire and cultures were working by minimal intercultural relationship regarding the dominated cultures. The indirect rule represents what was declared above. In contrast, this paper states that the Portuguese Empire and the Brazilian cultures were reporting a pattern of two-way of cultural influences. However, in Brazil, the relationship was violent and asymmetric. Hence, the Anglo-Saxon and the Portuguese Empires were both violent and asymmetric. However, they were working by different acculturation patterns.

The Anglo-Saxon and the Portuguese violent pasts may drive researchers and readers under anxious and anguished states. Charles Ralph Boxer (1959) was a British historian of Dutch and Portuguese colonial Empires. During the Salazar dictatorship, he studied the Portuguese imperial violence and the Portuguese Colonial Wars (1961-1974) in the Portuguese State of India and in the African colonies. The Boxer's aim was to display Portugal as a violent European Empire. On the Boxer's work, the Portuguese power ended to be reported as more violent than the Dutch and the British Empires. Therefore, the Boxer's work appeared as a defense mechanism (Freud, 1936) that splits violent impulses, and what was intolerable into bad and good objects (Klein, 1946). However, split is a maladaptive defense mechanism; it does not reduce anxiety, and it does not allow elaboration of violent impulses and thoughts. Boxer split and projected the unacceptable into the Portuguese culture. It is alike the paranoid position, because he splits only bad objects, and the Ego remains confined to them. It is also alike the cognitive dissonance described by Festinger (1962).

Gilberto Freyre was a Brazilian researcher educated with Boas. One day Gilberto Freyre observed Afro-Brazilian sailors disembarking in Brooklyn, New York. Freyre's ambivalent emotions regarding the racial composition of deprived Brazilian sailors inspired his research on the cultural formation of Brazil. He returned to Brazil and he described a clear picture of his reality, instead of to be guided by Anglo-Saxon academic concerns.

According to Freyre (1986/1933), the Brazilian culture was done by fusion and by asymmetric relationships. It encompasses two lessons. The first lesson is to display that all cultures, all ethnic groups are done by interaction and fusion. The second one is that Freyre integrated violence on his theoretical rationale. Freyre did not repress, and he did not split and project the violent impulses. Violence among cultures, races, and genders were sublimated on a new complex and broad reality. This rationalization states that all cultures are contributing to the configuration of a shared culture.

Freyre (1986/1933) provided an alternative historical point of view for the Western cultures. Yet, besides the Western historical backgrounds, it should be added different **perspectives** from different historical and cultural sources, even because individuals and cultures are today

interacting and mixing cultural traits more than **ever**. History and cross-cultural comparisons can be the solution to maladaptive behavior.

1. Portuguese intercultural relationships in Brazil

The Brazilian territory was inhabited by thousands of Indigenous semi-nomadic tribes who subsisted on hunting, fishing, gathering, and migrant agriculture. The European colonization of Brazil started in 1500 under the control and protection of the Portuguese Crown. Miscegenation started by intermarriage or by the force (Castro, 2016b; Clastres, 1974; Ribeiro, 1977). Castro Alves and José de Alencar were Brazilians Romantic novelists (Indianism) of the 19th century who praised the indigenous cultural traits, as Montaigne (n/d; 1595) did before. Later, Afro-Brazilians were brought to Brazil as slaves (Kilomba, 2010). In 1822, Brazil declared independence from Portugal. The Brazilian independence started the European immigration towards Brazil (Castro, 2016c; Schaden, 1967; Willems, 1980).

1.1 Gilberto Freyre

Gilberto Freyre (1900-1987) was a Brazilian sociologist and anthropologist. He was educated in Brazil and in the United States of America at the Baylor University, and still at the Columbia University with Franz Boas. In 1933, Freyre wrote *The Masters and the Slaves: A study in the development of Brazilian civilization* (Freyre, 1986/1933). He stressed a cross-cultural comparison among the Portuguese colonization in Brazil and other Europeans settlements; mainly the Anglo-Saxon. The Anglo-Saxon culture was not doing cultural adaptation regarding the oppressed cultures. According to Freyre (1961), the Anglo-Saxons were assimilating the dominated cultures: ". . . from a sociological point of view . . . the selection should be only in one direction." (p. 58).

Freyre (1986/1933) reported mutual interaction and reciprocal intercultural influences. He was reporting the cultural influences from the oppressed minorities, and he was also reporting that the European dominant culture was learning with the dominated non-European cultures (Braudel, 1943; Holanda, 1948; Ribeiro, 1977, 1995). One year after the main work of Freyre (1986/1933), the psychoanalyst and anthropologist Artur Ramos (1934) also stated that

African-Brazilians were not inferior regarding Europeans (Ramos, 1942). Regardless the asymmetric power relationship, the outcome was a culture of fusion (LaFromboise, Coleman, & Gerton, 1998). Furthermore, the emerging culture was allowing the existence of diversity and of cultural maintenance. For instance, the Candomblé and the Umbanda religions are representing different cultural mixtures (Bastide, 1971), and both reported the Indigenous and mainly the African cultures.

1.2 Roger Bastide

The French anthropologist Roger Bastide (1898-1974) was a professor in Brazil. Bastide displayed a culture of fusion grounded on the African-Brazilian religions. Bastide was influenced by the work of Freyre (Leal, 2011). Herskovits (1967) reported how the Afro-Americans were not in a passive position regarding European rulers. Bastide stated that African-Brazilians often just learned European cultural features to mask their own cultural maintenance (Bastide, 1971, 1968; Ferretti, 1995; Peixoto, 2000). The Bastide's work is also close to the antagonist acculturation point to view (Devereux, & Loeb, 1943; Hirano, 2010; Rudmin, 2003), and it is selective (Taft, R. 2007). In short, Freyre and Bastide reported reciprocal cultural influences (Castro, 2016d); ruler group and minorities learned, they interacted, mixed, and created a new culture with internal diversity and with cultural maintenance.

2. The Portuguese relationship with Japan

2.1 The *Historia do Japam* of Luís de Fróis

Luís de Fróis (1532-1597) born in Lisbon. In 1563, he arrived in Japan. In Hirado, he learned the Japanese language, and he preached the Catholic Faith. Between 1565 and 1576, he lived in Kyoto. Fróis and the Father Vilela (1526-1572) established a close relationship with the Shogun Oda Nobunaga, and they learned the local customs. Besides, the *Historia do Japam* (1976, 1981, 1982, 1983, 1984), the Fróis legacy is composed of letters, a book about a Christian Japanese embassy sent to Rome (Fróis, 1993b), and by a book that stressed a

comparison between the European and the Japanese cultures (Fróis, 2001, 1993a; Lévi-Strauss, 1998).

The *Historia do Japam* was demanded in 1583 by the chief Jesuit priest; Alessandro Valignano. Fróis started to write the manuscript in 1585, and he ended it in 1594. However, according to Valignano, the manuscript was too long in order to acquire social support from Europe and to work as an acculturative handbook for the Jesuits. The *Historia do Japam* manuscript was published in 1926 in Germany. A second publication took place in Japan in 1938. The Portuguese publication just took place in 1976.

In Japan, during the 16th century, the Portuguese culture was a European minority who tried to learn the Japanese culture in order to change it and to get a position of power in the Japanese society (Castro, 2016a). The Japanese culture also learned cultures traits from the European and Catholic cultures. The result was a mixed culture, which is still visible, for example, in the kakure Christians (Higashibaba, 2001; Lidin, 2002; Nakai, 2003; Pina, 2001; Tolosana, 2005).

2.2 The travels of Fernão Mendes Pinto

The travels of Mendes Pinto (Catz, 1989, Pinto, 1989/1614) was written by Fernão Mendes Pinto. On the Portuguese original version, it is called *Peregrinação* (Pilgrimage). Fernão Mendes Pinto (1509-10?-1583) was an adventurer, explorer, merchant, and novelist. He sailed to India in 1537, and he returned to Portugal in 1558. He was one of the first Europeans to encounter Japan (Catz, 1981). Pilgrimage was written between 1569 and 1578 (Catz, 1989), and the book became famous in Europe. The book employed autobiographic, historical, and fancy sources (Catz, 1978, 1989).

Fernão Mendes Pinto reported the Portuguese plasticity in order to get cultural adjustment to foreign cultures. According to Freyre (1959), Mendes Pinto was the paradigm of the Portuguese cultural plasticity (Souza, 2001). However, Pinto regretted the violence produced by the intercultural contacts. Hence, Pinto wanted to return to Portugal, and he perceived it as unchanged. It is important to notice the contradiction, because the Portuguese were reported

as very plastic at learning second cultures, but Portugal was perceived as unchanged. In short, the Brazilian and the Japanese cases reported the Portuguese on different power positions (Foucault, 1980), and both cases reported interaction, reciprocal cultural influences, and still cultures of fusion.

3 Comparative characterization of North-American Anglo-Saxon culture

Detocqueville (2002/1835) described the North-American culture under a dynamic process of fusion, hence under construction. However, almost one century and a half later, Mason (1955) complained that the North-American culture was doing a great effort to define ruled cultures, regardless that the pervasive Anglo-Saxon culture was portrayed with no cultural content. On the current article, it is stated that is possible to outline the North-American culture by its cultural borders (Barth, 1969), thus by comparative interaction with other cultures, and by its historical legacy (Mazlish, 2013).

The North-American historical legacy (the USA and Canada) lies mainly in the British WASP culture. The British Empire emerged after the Seven Years War (1755-1764) as the worldwide pervasive culture. The British Empire approached the rest of the World by a social dominance point of view, and by a sense of superiority (Adler, 1925; Rudmin, 2011; Rudmin, Wang, & Castro, 2016). On the contrary, the Portuguese Empire was already a peripheral culture (Braudel, 1983, 1987; Hobsbawm, 1995), even before the independence of Brazil in 1822. Besides the social dominance point of view and the sense of superiority, the North-American culture can be described as a place of hope (Mazlish, 2013). Yet, it is important to state that Brazil was also perceived as the New World, for instance, by Jesuits. The North-American New World was perceived as a place where the European faults and sins would be redeemed (Mazlish, 2013). The WASP North-American culture worked by the puritan predestination, which led to confine the social relationships to ingroup, to reduce the intercultural relationships with outgroups (Tajfel, 1974), and to the individualistic position:

It was in fact only the most extreme form of that exclusive trust in God in which we are here interested. It comes out for instance in the strikingly frequent repetition, especially in the English Puritan literature, of warnings against any trust in the aid of friendship of men. Even the amiable Baxter counsels deep distrust of even one's

closest friend, and Bailey directly exhorts to trust no one and to say nothing compromising to anyone... (Weber, 2001/1904-1905, p. 62)

Detocqueville (2002/1835) noticed that miscegenation was an aspiration on the Anglo-Saxon North-American culture. However, he also perceived it as doubtful. Almost one century and a half later, Myrdal (1944) described the American dilemma between the Republican values and the discriminatory reality. Yet, Detocqueville reported already the Anglo-Saxon minimal intercultural relationship, 'Thus while the French exercised no salutary influence over the Indians, the English have always remained alien from them'. (Detocqueville, 2002/1835, p. 379).

After the **Civil Rights Movement** (Glazer, 1993, 1997) the minimal intercultural interaction has its political expression on the multicultural model. The latter has a good trait; the minority cultural maintenance (in comparison with the forced assimilation). However, it holds intercultural interaction, and stresses social differences on cultures that are living in the same space.

In the USA the minimal intercultural relationship worked differently according to the cultural domains; it was more racial (biological) than religious. For instance, today Afro-Americans are largely Protestants. They were almost assimilated to the Protestant culture (including the idea of predestination, and the consequent minimal interaction). However, in Brazil, the Candomblé and the Umbanda are mixed religions. The Afro-Brazilian religions are reporting more African cultural maintenance than the Protestant Black Churches. The Afro-Brazilian religions are also reporting the Catholic influence, the mixtures, and the minority agency (Bastide, 1971). In the North-American culture, the racial mixture almost did not take place. The WASP culture missed the Detocqueville (2002/1835) expectation, and the Myrdal (1944) dilemma is still present.

On the beginning of the 20th-century, Taft, D. R. (1969/1923) was puzzled and concerned, due to the blackness of the Portuguese immigrants in New England; the Portuguese Europeans were living with half-breeds, and with Africans on the same residential space. For the current

article, the most interesting fact is that Portuguese were used to mix with Africans. However, it was perceived as strange and dangerous on the WASP culture.

António Luis Santos da Costa is the current Prime Minister of Portugal, he is half-breed; his father was from Portuguese Goa (India), and his mother is European Portuguese. When he took the Portuguese political power, it was not a big topic. Portuguese people just took it as a normal fact, and he is perceived as a half-breed. In the USA, the election of Obama was a buzz matter, and Americans perceived him as a black person, and not as a highly educated half-breed person. It reports how Anglo-Saxons sometimes perceived ethnic reality by a binary and absolutism judgment, a consideration that works by separation and by choosing just one option, even when the reality is displaying mixtures and it is complex.

The racial reality can report the difference between Brazil and USA. In the United States of America the percentage of intermarriages is low (Batson, Qian, & Lichter, 2006; Qian, & Lichter, 2007). Yet, in Brazil, the miscegenation is an observable reality (Bastide, 1973; Braudel, 1943; Herskovits, 1967; Holanda, 1998; Nabuco, 1908; Ribeiro, 1995).

The USA and the Brazilian census are useful to reinforce the cross-cultural comparison. In 2010, the overwhelming majority (97%) of the USA population reported only one race, and just 3% of the total population reported more than one race. In the USA, there are 72% of whites, 13% of African-Americans, 5% of Asians, 0.9% American Indians and Alaska Natives, and 0.2% of Native Hawaiians and Other Pacific Islanders (U. S. Census Bureau, 2011). In Brazil, according to the *Instituto Brasileiro de Geografia e Estatística* (IBGE, 2011), in 2010, the population was composed of 47,7% of Whites, 43% of Pardos, 7, 6% of Blacks, 1,1 of Asians, and 0,42% of Indigenous citizens. The label Pardos is including all possible mixtures among whites, Indigenous, and Afro-Brazilians.

Regardless the ethnic difference between the USA and Brazil, it is important to state that the mixtures of cultures (races) are not a solution by themselves for the intercultural conflicts. As Lévi-Strauss (1952) wrote, race is just a main factor that may hide a more fundamental problem; the difficulty of live together.

4. New worldwide conditions

Nowadays, the world is facing climate changes (Lovelock, 1972), economic exhaustion, nuclear war, an increase of intercultural contacts, faster migrations, and faster cultural changes. The world is interdependent (e.g. at economic and at cultural domains), it has several main cultural centers (e.g. China, India, USA, Brazil, Russia, Japan). There is a boost of the available information (Serres, 2012; Stiegler, 2015), and there are easier and faster communications (Hobsbawm, 1995), and finally the ethnic identities are intertwined (Serres, 2012). Today, the ethnic identity is formulated beyond the tribe, the family, and the State in an individualistic and complex way (Bauman, 2004; Lyotard, 1988).

The Freyre's work (1986/1933) is useful to display that it is necessary to take into account the historical backgrounds. The Portuguese historical background is different regarding the Anglo-Saxon. The Portuguese historical legacy is done by mutual interaction, by reporting to learn about other cultures, and by praising the fusion of cultures. The Anglo-Saxon culture is done by the minimal interaction (Bastide, 1973; Detocqueville, 2002/1835; Myrdal, 1944; Serres, 1991; Todd, 1994) among the different cultures, and it barely reports to learn about other cultures.

Violence and the social dominance regarding other cultures are similar between the Anglo-Saxon and the Portuguese cultures. However, both cultures had different approaches regarding intercultural contact. The shared intercultural violence and social dominance may drive researchers and readers to an anxious state (Rudmin, 2014). Violence can be universal and an ordinary feature (Arendt, 1958; Benjamin, 1978; Lévi-Strauss, 1952). Yet, it may paralyze further action, and it may drive to defense mechanisms as splitting and projecting.

4.1 Solutions

According to Morin (2003), science must be designed with ethical and social concerns. History is often written by the "winners" (Goody, 2006). However, in a more and more globalized (Türken, & Rudmin, 2013) and postcolonial world, it is necessary to combine different

historical narratives. Freyre combined the Portuguese, the Indigenous, and the Afro-Brazilians cultures into a new one. He reported interaction, fusion, and agency on all cultures. On a similar manner, History should combine more historical backgrounds, besides the Anglo-Saxon and the Western European cultural backgrounds.

The literature of History of Long-Term (Braudel, 1958) is useful in order to accomplish that task. Another historical source can be the historiography that crosses different periods of times, sources, cultures, and languages. Often, it is called World History, Global History or Transnational History (Manning, 2003; Subrahmanyam, 2004a, b, 2012; 2014; Subrahmanyam, & Muzaffar, 2007). This historiography can lead to cross-cultural comparisons, thus to confront the Western dilemmas and contradictions. The World History also can add new information, and to produce shared narratives with at least two-way of cultural influences (Bayly, 2004; Gruzinski, 1999, 2004; Manning, 2003).

The mutual historical narrative is a symbolic artifact (Vygotsky, 1978/1930, 1986), because shared meanings can empower basic trust (Erikson, 1950), and decrease the splitting and projecting maladaptive defense mechanisms (Freud, 1936) of the paranoid-schizoid position (Klein, 1946, 1964). Higher defense mechanism can lead to a stronger elaboration; mindfulness (curiosity, openness, and acceptance); sublimation; tolerance regarding what is different; and rationalization with a permanent critic point of view.

The shared History does not reduce the cultural diversity (Feyerabend, 1993). The current article states that a shared and mutual historical narrative can decrease the reproduction of social dominance position, and of the associated victimization and anxiety about annihilation. The Anglo-Saxon superiority complex hides an inferiority complex; the historical cross-cultural comparisons can decrease the cognitive bias related to the illusory superiority. It can also promote peace (Christie, 2006; Rudmin, 2012), and soft power (Nye, 2011), because attachment (Bowlby, 1969) drives to empathy, and it avoids the psychopathic position (Meloy, 1988).

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